

IMPROVING THE LEXICAL SYSTEM OF THE NAMES OF NATIONAL GAMES

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Abstract: The article focuses on the improvement of the names of national games in the lexical system, the issues of national game names and their lexical classification. The article presents the lexical classification of the names of the national national games according to their status, as well as the division of the games into lexical classification forms in relation to the processes such as the place of appearance, the state of formation, and the names and naming of the games. This means that game names and their naming issues are a very complicated process.

Key words: folk game names, classification, flow, nationality, lexical aspect

In order to speak clearly and clearly about national games, their naming and names, it is necessary to carry out their scientific classification. They are described as follows: National games at all stages of human development embodied a number of characteristics of the people of their time, such as life, lifestyle, working conditions, nationality, religion, names and designations. As a result, they served to educate the participants in the qualities of agility, endurance, creativity, enthusiasm, strength, independent thinking and the presence of sacred names for a person.

In national games, in particular, in the content and names of children's games, along with the qualities of agility, endurance, creativity, enthusiasm, strength, light humor, competition, and team unity are more noticeable. Uzbek national games can be classified in different ways from the point of view of physical education science and naming aspects. For example, it is natural that the classification of national games is related to the age of the participants, the

classification of national games is related to gender, the classification of national games is related to the season, the classification of national games is related to the place where they are played, the classification of national games is related to the profession, and the classification of national games is related to the region. At this point, it should be noted that the classification of the types of khadq games and the classification of the names of national games are different classifications.

Currently, the main task of the national games is to ensure the education of children in accordance with the requirements of our society with their content, essence and methodology of application to young people, as well as their names and naming, to develop their moral and willpower capabilities, to give them names, their naming and renaming, formation of knowledge, skills and qualifications, characteristic features and qualities of students.

We would like to emphasize here that national games are a general concept, and national national games are a relatively specific concept. Therefore, it is appropriate to first use the term of names of national national games, and then use the term of naming national games.

In the ancient educational system that has come down to us from our ancestors, every game has been widely used as a means of personality formation. The forward-thinking representatives of the managers of the games understood their educational value very cleverly. They believed that it is possible to find out children's behavior during the game in relation to any situation, identify their negative and positive qualities more easily, and apply better measures to eliminate inappropriate behavior. Therefore, even in those times, taking into account the age characteristics of children, the question of naming games suitable for them and choosing them according to the purpose was raised.

It can be seen from these that each of the national national games was given a special name by the wise, knowledgeable and far-seeing representatives of the nation. Because national games as a separate system of onomastic units of the Uzbek language should be lexically-semantically classified according to their

specific names, the possibility of naming, the possibility of renaming, the nature of playing and the circumstances of their application.

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